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THE NEED FOR DIGITAL WATER IN A GREEN EUROPE

EU H2020 projects' contribution to the implementation
and strengthening of EU environmental policy

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Abstract

The purpose of this present document prepared by the Policy Action Group of the ICT4Water cluster is to highlight those possibilities that a more digitalised water industry can offer in support of the revision of the Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive, the implementation of the revised EU Drinking Water Directive and the achievement of those goals established by the long-term environmental and climate strategies of the European Union. The document has been prepared after a process of consultation with members of consortia of about 60 EU-funded projects from ICT4Water cluster who were asked to complete a detailed questionnaire. After an initial analysis undertaken by an editorial board, individual leaders of specific projects were contacted in order to obtain further, in-depth information.

The resulting paper promotes the central role of the water sector within what is known as the *Twin Transition* to a green and digital economy as established in the objectives of the European Green Deal and above all recommends actions that would not only improve the management of the water sector as a whole within the context of the circular economy but also contribute significantly to the objectives of European environmental strategies that have been proposed during the period 2019-2020.

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Introduction

The original ambitions of the present European Commission to establish, promote and sustain a globally competitive, climate-neutral and digitalised society have not waivered in the wake of the dramatic events of 2020. On the contrary, the resolve of the European Union as a whole to achieve the objectives described by Ursula von der Leyen in 2019¹ has been strengthened as a result of the sanitary, socio-political and economic crisis caused by the appearance of COVID-19. As Commissioner Virginijus Sinkevičius made clear at a meeting with representatives of the European Water Alliance on the 2nd of October 2020, the key strategy for the period 2019-2024 is and will be the twin transition to a green and digital economy firmly grounded in the objectives of the European Green Deal. To become the World's first climate-neutral continent involves the implementation of measures that embrace concepts such as the *Farm to Fork Strategy* and the *New Circular Economy Action Plan* in order to 'preserve Europe's natural environment'.²

A coherent, inclusive and, above all, sustainable society must involve all stakeholders in a transparent process of co-creation, implementation and post-implementation analysis of a broad range of policies. These policies should reflect the needs and visions of the public, private, research, citizen and cultural sectors at supranational, national, regional and municipal levels. A top-down and bottom-up approach must be adhered to in order to acquire the necessary societal consensus to guarantee effective policy continuity that will extend beyond the mandate of the present European administration. As the United Nations has made clear, '*...one of the major challenges facing the world community as it seeks to replace unsustainable development patterns with environmentally sound and sustainable development is the need to activate a sense of common purpose on behalf of all sectors of society. The chances of forging such a sense of purpose will depend on the willingness of all sectors to participate in genuine social partnership and dialogue, while recognising the independent roles, responsibilities and special capacities of each.*'³ In the same way, environmental policy areas must put aside inter and intra-sectoral rivalries and fragmentation so that the essential interplay between the principal aspects of the environment are addressed correctly. The nexus, the reciprocal and mutual action and reaction between the inextricably linked spheres of water, energy, food and the eco-system (WEFE NEXUS) must be understood and acted upon accordingly if Europe is to successfully satisfy what von der Leyen described as '*the passion, conviction and energy of the millions of our young people making their voice heard on our streets and in our hearts*'⁴.

The Water Sector is (and must be) at the core of the environmental debate. Water is, quite simply, the most essential natural resource on the planet. Global water challenges affecting water resources, such as climate change, population growth, increasing urbanisation and ageing infrastructure, continue to intensify. The latest UN data estimates that 3.6 billion people, almost half the global population, live in areas that are potentially water-scarce at least one month per year and by 2050, more than 5 billion people could suffer water shortages due to climate change, increased demand and polluted supplies. The World Bank

¹ Von der Leyen, U. (2019) A Union that strives for more. My agenda for Europe. https://ec.europa.eu/commission/sites/beta-political/files/political-guidelines-next-commission_en.pdf

² Von der Leyen, U. (2019).

³ United Nations Environment Programme Decision: 27.2.

⁴ Von der Leyen, U. (2019).

(2016) and the World Economic Forum (2010) regard water as the most likely natural cause of armed conflict in the 21st Century. No attempt to establish a *Green Economy* can be successful if it does not involve the water sector in all its facets. An important advance towards such progress faithfully reflects the second factor of the Twin Transition: digitalisation.

The global water sector is changing as it begins to embrace a digital transformation, to drive sustainable water management. The transformation for utilities is a migration from a data-rich environment to more of a knowledge-rich environment.

Digital technology applications such as remote sensing, asset management (operation and maintenance), resources allocation and prioritisation, customer engagement, predictive analytics (e.g. asset failure prediction), artificial intelligence, augmented and virtual reality (e.g. water utility maintenance and training) and cybersecurity provide the means to dramatically advance the management of water. Digital water represents the very essence of the Twin Transition.

Internet of Things (IoT) technologies, including commodity sensors, data analysis, cloud computing, intelligence amplification (or cognitive augmentation) and blockchain, entail new possibilities to analyse, automate, correct in real time, forecast and minimise risks. They can help water and sanitation companies address many of the challenges they face, such as extending the useful life of ageing assets; reducing leaks, attacks, and other anomalies in the distribution network; improving water quality, service levels and the reliability of the supply; promoting water conservation, managing energy and materials use or increasing turnover through greater operational efficiency. Furthermore, digitalisation can contribute to reducing costs for water utilities and their customers, engaging end-users and influencing behavioural patterns. Finally, but closely linked to the creation of this document, digital water management can and must provide the basis for a more purposeful design and revision of existing and future statutory legislation.

The Policy Action Group of the ICT4Water cluster have investigated the challenges that have been overcome and the barriers that are yet to be dismantled in water sector. These enable the opportunities to promote the value of digitalisation in combination and in collaboration with other technological progress for WEF E NEXUS management. The following observations and recommendations seek to contribute to the achievement of the new Europe that modern society demands and which the European Commission has promised.

1. HOW DIGITALISATION OF WATER INFRASTRUCTURES CONTRIBUTES TO REDUCING OPEX OR CAPEX FOR UTILITIES OR AUTHORITIES

Digital monitoring solutions can help **to optimise the management and control of wastewater treatment plants**, which may result in higher degrees of energy efficiency as well reductions in chemicals used and carbon or other gas emissions. For example, in the SMART-Plant project⁵, benefits comprehending OPEX (Operating expenses) savings and additional revenues, were calculated to range between 1 and 7 EUR/population equivalent (PE) per year, while initial CAPEX (Capital expenses) for monitoring technology ranged between 6 to 20 EUR/PE per year. The INTEGROIL project⁶ developed and demonstrated a decision support system that was capable of selecting and activating different modular treatments of an integrated solution for wastewater treatment at oil and gas industrial facilities, providing fit-for purpose water as a function of the quality of input wastewater. A demonstration in a pilot plant proved that the amount of reclaimed water for reuse could be increased by more than 50% in relation to the initial situation, ensuring water quality requirements in a continuous way.

In the context of **hydraulic optimisation, failure prediction and leakage detection** in water distribution networks, digital approaches making use of sensors and smart meter data and intelligent algorithms are already widely spread. For example, aggregated machine sensor data is employed for infrastructure condition monitoring whilst smart water meter data is used to analyse anomalies in consumption to identify leakages. However, there is still a high potential to improve OPEX and CAPEX savings. Minimising the time of leakage detection and consequently water losses results in lower electricity and construction costs. In the SCOREwater project⁷, predictive maintenance was achieved by monitoring sedimentation, turbidity and water level in the wastewater network using a new innovative sensor technology which has the potential to be extremely cost efficient and demands low or no maintenance. With regards to hydraulic optimisation, WISDOM project⁸ investigated a new adapted mixed-integer differential evolution algorithm for demand optimised management integrating smart meters, intelligent sensing, water analytics and in-house displays to encourage water conservation through behavioural change. Simulation results on a pilot water network confirmed the effectiveness of the proposed methodology and suggested that 23.7% energy and maintenance cost savings can be achieved, if adaptive pricing is applied to all the pumping stations⁹. In addition, the benefit obtained by reducing losses will, in some cases, be much more important in saving water resources, rather than in terms of saving money. Nevertheless, one should note that since the installation of sensors might induce additional CAPEX and the potential replacement of part of the network (in the case of detected leakages) would be also linked to OPEX, achievable cost reductions might be neutralised by the aforementioned additional costs. In digital-water.city (DWC) project, machine learning algorithms are deployed to support predictive maintenance of drinking water wells and optimize short and long term rehabilitation strategies. Similar solutions are also implemented for sewer networks such as the SEMA tool¹⁰.

Digital solutions can be also proved to be beneficial with regards to the **inspection and maintenance** of water infrastructures. The Digital-Water.City (DWC) project¹¹ developed and tested a smart combination of high-definition camera, sewer-cleaning nozzle and wireless communication technology which is aimed at increasing interoperability between cleaning and inspection teams and boosting the performance of sewer cleaning processes

⁵ <https://www.smart-plant.eu/>

⁶ <https://integroil.eu/>

⁷ <https://www.scorewater.eu/>

⁸ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/619795>

⁹ <https://royalsocietypublishing.org/doi/full/10.1098/rspa.2017.0879>

¹⁰ <https://www.kompetenz-wasser.de/en/project/sema-berlin-2/>

¹¹ <https://www.digital-water.city/>

by saving time, fuel and water compared to conventional cleaning processes. This is expected to result in lower OPEX.

Fiware4Water project¹² has developed a decision support system allowing one **to optimise drinking water production** by choosing between different reservoirs to feed the drinking water treatment plants for the city of Athens. The choice will be made principally on the basis of continuous online turbidity measurement in the reservoirs. By reducing the quantity of particles suspended or dissolved in untreated water, treatment costs are also reduced, thus decreasing OPEX.

As technology selection and benchmarking for plant retrofitting have become more challenging due to the large number of possible plant-designs for given wastewater treatment problems, data-driven approaches, such as big data and artificial intelligence, are becoming integral aspects of **decision support systems**. Such approaches were also developed and demonstrated in the projects AQUANESS¹³, NextGen¹⁴, Project Ô¹⁵ and SMART-Plant. Employing such tools, digital process information can be used to simulate possible configurations of a plant for varying design parameters (e.g. inflow conditions) in order to **identify the optimal configuration of wastewater management and reuse systems** at different scales. Similarly, the so-called 'smart matchmaking platforms' can prove to be an invaluable tool for water utilities. To indicate, the platform developed by DWC are capable of tackling complex problems and coordinating the allocation of treated wastewater for agricultural irrigation, although there may be uncertainty regarding demand, weather, and prices. All these approaches lead to improved, informed planning and decision-making which can result in a reduction of CAPEX and OPEX for the plant operators. However, although the quantification of the benefits and avoided costs is complicated due to the lack of knowledge regarding the potential opportunity costs occurring from an inappropriate plant design and/or operation.

Further cost savings can be achieved through **demand side management measures** and **citizen science approaches** in monitoring. For example, in the SmartH2O project¹⁶, a gamification platform provides transparent and quasi-real time access to water data consumption. This platform sends signals to water consumers about their water use and motivates them to modify their consumption according to the current situation (e.g. a drought). In this way, SmartH2O has had an impact in more than 1,000 households in Spain and Switzerland, achieving substantial water savings, reducing leaks and supply costs. Some users in Valencia registered on the SmartH2O platform showed average water savings of more than 5%, as opposed to a control group of users not registered on the platform, whose consumption increased by approximately 15%. In the case study of the city of Sabadell, Spain, the digital social platform of the POWER project¹⁷ provided consumers with information to encourage better management of resources and a reduction of drinking water consumption, replaced by non-potable water. A real-time information system enabled consumers to collect information about the quality and conditions of service throughout their distribution network. By connecting city inhabitants through a digital social network, citizens are able to identify different levels of water quality for drinking and non-potable water, take appropriate decisions and openly judge and voice their opinions concerning the allocation and use of local water resources. Such behavioural change of consumers can contribute to a more efficient use of the water distribution infrastructure by smoothing demand peaks, reducing both water consumption and energy demand for pumping, and consequently lowering the OPEX.

The MONOCLE project¹⁸ developed high-resolution optical and citizen science monitoring methodologies that are capable of **identifying pollution at nutrient point sources**.

¹² <http://www.fiware4water.eu/>

¹³ <http://www.aquanes-h2020.eu/>

¹⁴ <https://nextgenwater.eu/>

¹⁵ <http://eu-project-o.eu/>

¹⁶ SMARTH2O <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/619172>

¹⁷ <https://www.power-h2020.eu/>

¹⁸ <https://monocle-h2020.eu/>

These monitoring tools include low-cost nutrient kits that can be used by non-experts to identify and report point source pollution at a micro-scale (individual streams and tributaries). The cost of such methods is in the order of 20 EUR for a citizen science kit with multiple uses, plus the cost of training and engaging with citizen groups. Another example of a citizen-science approach is the use of drone imagery tools. These off-the-shelf hobby platforms can be employed for water monitoring but require support from experts to generate optimal flight paths and post-process the imagery. However, the cost of the platform (200-1000 EUR) conforms to what a project's survey described as '*suitable for operational use*' and is much cheaper than the cost of investigated reference systems (10,000-40,000 EUR). Nevertheless, the main objective of digital water monitoring is more to improve the reliability and performance of the water services provided by a water utility than to reduce OPEX. However, Fiware4Water demonstration cases¹⁹ proved that it can constitute a further benefit to the adoption of water monitoring measures/tools.

In relation to **reducing urban flooding and CSO spills**, the CENTAUR project²⁰ and subsequent work provided evidence that CAPEX can be reduced for future expenditure by implementing relatively lower cost solutions. Such solutions include, for example, **local autonomous data driven** in-sewer flow control systems, rather than building more costly new storage tanks or centralised model predictive real-time control systems. Furthermore, the WISDOM project showcased that **data driven approaches** for CSO time-series predictions help to reduce both the cost and time associated with model development and calibration in comparison to hydrological-hydraulic modeling approaches, whilst complying with regulations established by environment agencies and/or local authorities.

With regards to **data reporting processes**, digital solutions can provide valuable input, with regards, for example, to water quality monitoring designed to support the implementation of the Water Framework Directive (WFD). The European Union and European Space Agency currently boast the most advanced range of satellite-based instruments designed to observe optical water quality.²¹ Therefore, most of the costs associated with satellite-based monitoring of surface waters have already been met. Consequently, national authorities should take the greatest advantage of this and encourage the use of satellite-based monitoring to complement national and statutory monitoring and reporting.

Although there exists much evidence from recent research regarding cost savings due to intelligent and data-driven solutions, there are still certain bottlenecks hampering the implementation of digital solutions in practice:

- Wastewater treatment systems are critical infrastructures for society and thus require special security measures. Progress regarding the uptake of digital solutions by utilities has been hindered by a perceived risk of lack of security. This is a risk that can be minimised through the use of appropriate technologies and tools to secure the Digital Water Systems from external intervention, although such security tools have not yet been broadly accepted by the water sector (ref. STOP-IT project²²).
- Even though digital solutions can reduce the OPEX and, in some cases, CAPEX of water infrastructures, they represent, in the minds of many, as something which requires initial investments. For example, smart metering helps to reduce leakages, thus contributing to a reduced OPEX. However, the installation of sensors and the

¹⁹ <https://www.fiware4water.eu/demo-cases/greece-raw-water-supply-optimisation-case>

²⁰ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/641931>

²¹ Papathanasopoulou et al. (2019) Satellite-assisted monitoring of water quality to support the implementation of the Water Framework Directive DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3463051.

²² <https://stop-it-project.eu/>

potential replacement of parts of the network (e.g. when a leakage is detected) result in additional CAPEX. The break-even points for economic investment might vary to a great extent depending on the water supply system in question.

To meet these major challenges and to support success stories described above, the following policy-related actions are recommended:

Recommendation 1.1

As results from the latest research projects demonstrate, citizen science approaches facilitated, supported and promoted by the use of digital technologies can be valuable elements of monitoring approaches, capable of achieving a high level of participation and should therefore be fostered by local authorities and utilities.

Recommendation 1.2

The sharing of monitoring data by using open data minimises costs (e.g. linked to digital twins) for stakeholders and customers, whilst helping to minimise the miscommunication costs and ensuing legal actions. Authorities should therefore strive for collaborative tools, offering **transparency** to all stakeholders involved. This would permit a greater alignment with EU water policy that demands greater transparency for the general public (e.g. Drinking Water Directive- DWD).

Recommendation 1.3

National authorities should take the greatest advantage of existing satellite and geo-referencing infrastructures (for example, GEOSS and COPERNICUS data) and available solutions to encourage the use of innovative monitoring approaches, including satellite-based monitoring to complement national and statutory monitoring and reporting. At the EU level, a stock-taking of a) the practical applications and implementation of satellite and geo-referencing in different Member States and b) their support for policy implementation and recommendations/guidance on good practices is strongly advised.

Recommendation 1.4

Employing resources made available as a result of a) the COVID recovery plan (financing the digitalisation of utilities, ensuring the interoperability of different services such as energy, wastewater²³ and IT networks) and b) the establishment of the *Twin Transition* as a political priority²⁴, support for sustainable financing tools and investments to reduce OPEX/CAPEX should be enhanced.

Recommendation 1.5

Authorities should include a requirement within public procurement procedures for the water sector whereby cost and benefit analysis that include estimates of OPEX/CAPEX and efforts to optimise them should be included whereby digital aspects (e.g. monitoring/metering) are taken into account.

²³ Wastewater = sewage, stormwater and combined sewage and stormwater.

²⁴ Von der Leyen, U. (2019) *A Union that strives for more. My agenda for Europe.*

https://ec.europa.eu/commission/sites/beta-political/files/political-guidelines-next-commission_en.pdf

2. THE CAPACITY OF THE DIGITALISATION OF THE WATER SECTOR TO ENGAGE WATER CONSUMERS AND INFLUENCE BEHAVIOUR

Digital water techniques can be applied at any point of the water life-cycle. Within a specific geographical area of any particular natural water system, the relationships between the natural resource and the utility, the utility and the customer and the customer and the environment are all open to improvement thanks to the employment of digital water.

By the use of websites, mobile phones and smart meter technologies, **end users can be engaged in the creation and implementation of local actions** whose objective is sustainability whilst bringing utilities closer to their customers through channels of communication and more efficient digital services. A number of projects within the ICT4WATER cluster²⁵ (e.g. SMARTH2O, INTCATCH²⁶, URBANWATER²⁷, NAIADES²⁸, GROUNDTRUTH 2.0²⁹, Fiware4Water and POWER) obtained evidence supporting this and alluded to the fact that there **exists a relationship between end-user awareness and a reduction in consumption**. The POWER project, for example, working in Jerusalem (IL), Milton Keynes and Leicester (UK) and Sabadell (ES) demonstrated that end-users are interested in becoming not only informed but truly engaged in local water policy creation and implementation. Enhanced corporate transparency and increased awareness for the conservation of natural resources are being created thanks to digitalisation as described by the SMARTH2O and URBANWATER projects. As Burritt and Christ (2016)³⁰ stated *"Not only are members of the public demanding that organisations treat natural resources such as water, air and soil with respect, government and non-government organisations are encouraging corporations to undertake activities in a manner that is economically, environmentally and socially sustainable [...] this is being brought about by the internet of things"*.

Digital water can lead to a greater understanding of water use patterns by the customer. The ICT4WATER projects, DWC and aqua3S³¹, illustrated the efficiency of an approach of clearly delivered information to a broader public so that the issue of pollution at source is better understood by the imaginative employment of augmented reality (AR) in the case of the former and a digital signal processing (DSP) in the example of the latter. Researchers involved in SMARTPLANT, NAIADES, POWER, PROJECT Ô and HYDROUSA³² projects observed a reduction of unpaid bills due to more personal monitoring of the amount of water one is using at home, a subsequent reduction of costs for the householder, (due to prompt detection of leakage) and a far more rapid response on the part of utilities to customer incidents. These initiatives have demonstrated the importance of the co-creation of the design of digital systems together with the target end-users, which also encourages continued post-project exploitation. The conclusions of NAIADES, POWER, PROJECT Ô and HYDROUSA would **advocate a research-supported, bottom-up approach**. HYDROUSA provides an excellent example of efficient digital irrigation

²⁵ <https://ict4water.eu/>

²⁶ <https://www.intcatch.eu/>

²⁷ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/318602/results>

²⁸ <https://naiades-project.eu/>

²⁹ <https://gt20.eu/>

³⁰ Burritt, R. and Christ, K. (2016). Industry 4.0 and environmental accounting: a new revolution?. Asian Journal of Sustainability and Social Responsibility. 1. 10.1186/s41180-016-0007-y.

³¹ <https://aqua3s.eu/>

³² <https://www.hydrousa.org/>

benefiting a rural community. Such benefits were clear for the target group in question: low-cost water monitoring, allowing effective irrigation of crops in areas with water scarcity, an effective prediction capability and increased water savings. SMART-PLANT demonstrated the transformation of a Wastewater Treatment Plant (WWTP) into a Blue Resource Centre through the simulation of a top-down tariff model. Such model would suggest public acceptance and its understanding due not only to the recovery and production of energy, nutrients and cellulose but also in great part to the direct reduction of water tariffs permitted by this circular economy approach.

Historically, the water industry has been notoriously efficient at ignoring “*concepts developed from within the economic and social sciences*”, as Rohner (2018)³³ pointed out. There exists the need to activate a sense of common purpose on behalf of all sectors of society. The chances of forging such a sense of purpose will depend on the willingness of all sectors to participate in genuine social partnership and dialogue while recognising the independent roles, responsibilities and special capacities of each (United Nations Environment Programme Decision: 27.2). This is being further investigated at present by Fiware4water project which is directly contributing to the United Nations World Water Quality Alliance. The opinion of the private sector, the public sector, academia and, perhaps most importantly, the opinion of the electorate or citizen must be sought, taken into account and engaged. These four elements constitute the Quadruple Helix or the Quintuple Helix if one includes cultural influences. Commissioner Moedas of the European Union stated in 2016 that “*The Citizen must be at the centre of open innovation and subsequent public policy*” (Elelman and Feldman, 2018)³⁴. The resulting behaviour change must be proved to be continuous and permanent. A sense of being a stakeholder in what is being implemented encourages hitherto uninvolved groups to remain active. A tangible economic or practical benefit as was seen by the HYDROUSA consortium where improved irrigation, **co-designed with the end-users**, was brought about within an acceptable period of Return on Investment (ROI) and which has, as a result, provided a study foundation for coherent future practices.

To meet these major challenges the following policy related actions are recommended:

Recommendation 2.1

Legislators/Authorities must ensure that end-user engagement is considered a priority in the co-creation and implementation of initiatives involving the use of digital water technology. The proactive involvement of all social sectors will further guarantee a broad social awareness, increase acceptance and facilitate subsequent political continuity involving all stakeholders of the Quadruple/Quintuple Helix.

³³ Rohner P. (2018) Water: A Megatrends Perspective. In: Biswas A., Tortajada C., Rohner P. (eds) Assessing Global Water Megatrends. Water Resources Development and Management. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-10-6695-5_2

³⁴ Elelman, R, Feldman, D.L. (2018) The future of citizen engagement in cities—The council of citizen engagement in sustainable urban strategies (ConCensus). Futures Volume 101, August 2018, Pages 80-91. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2018.06.012>

Recommendation 2.2

European Commission administrations including DG ENVIRONMENT, DG JRC and the Vice-Presidency for the Green Deal must further support the implementation of digital water technology in its role as an attractive, accessible and effective channel of communication (e.g. make use of distant/digital social platforms). Digital technology is capable of providing both efficient social platforms and constantly improved resources which enable an inter-sectoral dialogue at all levels. Information to a broad (hitherto uninformed) audience must be actively encouraged. This will contribute to the tangible improvement of both **top-down** and **bottom-up** approaches to the management of water, increase the number of better informed and more satisfied customers and permit a more probable acceptance of short-term increases in tariffs.

Recommendation 2.3

The Joint Research Centre of the European Commission to establish educational courses designed for water professionals regarding social engagement. Both supranational administrations and the water sector must understand the definition of end-user engagement to its full extent, why this is important and how to take actions. The courses must be clearly structured, efficiently implemented and adaptable to different geographical, technical and cultural realities at a river basin, regional and local levels.

3. HOW THE DIGITALISATION OF THE WATER SECTOR CAN CONTRIBUTE TO IMPROVED REGULATION DESIGN & IMPLEMENTATION

Digitalisation can improve the governance of pollution policies via monitoring and outlook tools using existing and developing new data sources (such as big data, IoT), models and interoperable data models. Digital solutions in the water sector can help to improve the **monitoring of the compliance with existing permits** for water abstraction and usage as well as emissions and discharges. Moreover, improved monitoring by employing digital solutions must be an essential requirement for the authorities when evaluating environmental and water use permit applications. Employing the DIANA platform (developed in DIANA project³⁵), water rights information provided by water authorities can be compared with irrigated area products. Following this approach, irrigated areas, both with and without water rights, can be detected and an evaluation of irrigation water volumes used by farmers can be made, wherever flowmeters are missing or not working. A similar approach has also been investigated for industrial discharges and emissions by SCOREwater and SMART-Plant projects.

Combined Sewer Overflow (CSO) events have various detrimental effects such as oxygen depletion, ammonia toxicity and hydrological stress on aquatic organisms. Digitalisation can support improved implementation and **compliance with the Water Framework Directive**, to address environmental pressures employing measures such as CSO control and the continuous upgrade of wastewater networks to avoid contamination. For example, within the DWC project, innovative devices for real-time bacterial measurements were developed permitting the rapid quantification of E.coli or enterococci concentrations and emitting real-time automatic alerts. As a next step, such information can also be employed for predicting water pollution based on the combination of meteorological data and water quality sensors, as investigated by SCOREwater in Göteborg.

Digital solutions can support improved implementation and **compliance with the Urban Wastewater Directive (UWWTD) by detecting and locating illegal connections and extraneous inflows** in sewer systems. For example, a distributed temperature sensing technique developed by DWC was tested in Berlin to detect and locate illegal connections and extraneous inflows in sewer systems. This technique used using fibre-optic cables as large temperature sensors or flexible units for real-time water quality monitoring with multi-parameter sensors and automatic sampling. DWC also developed a low-cost monitoring technique, based on the deployment of a network of innovative low-cost temperature sensors to estimate emissions from combined sewer overflows (CSO) across a large number of points in a sewer system.

Digitalisation can **support the implementation of the new EU regulation for water reuse**. In HYDROUSA, the integration of digital solutions within decentralised water treatment systems (including individual and/or appropriate systems-IAS in accordance with the UWWTD) enabled the plant operators to achieve a dynamic water quality monitoring at different places along the treatment chain. The aim was to ensure that the reclaimed water meets the requirements for unrestricted/restricted agricultural irrigation and that potential excess discharges to water bodies are in compliance with environmental permits. In HYDROUSA, a full control and monitoring apparatus permits operators to track and trace the reclaimed water distributed for irrigation. This digital tracking and tracing capability allows for a clear understanding of the role of water from various sources in fulfilling demand.

Finally, digital solutions in the water sector can also be beneficial in **establishing sustainable water pricing policies**. The SMARTH2O project developed a dynamic pricing tool which can design new water pricing policies that can influence water consumption behaviour to meet sustainability targets.

³⁵ <https://diana-h2020.eu/en/>

There are still, however, certain challenges to be addressed in the context of improved regulation design and implementation based on digital solutions:

- EU regulations have correctly identified CSOs as an important source of contamination and urban flooding. Promoting appropriate monitoring and controlling all CSO structures is therefore needed to avoid the detrimental effects described above as well as to achieve and maintain a high ecological quality of the receiving water. Two of the main limitations with regards to CSOs to date have delayed the implementation of extensive monitoring of CSOs: i) the high number of CSO structures per municipality or catchment area and ii) the high cost of the flow-monitoring equipment available on the market to measure CSO events. Moreover, there are technical constraints connected to accessing and installing monitoring equipment in certain CSO structures. As a result, utilities lack information concerning the behaviour of the network and potential impacts on local water bodies.
- Remote sensing solutions can be an effective tool to identify unauthorized water uses (see examples from SCOREwater and DWC above). However, their use varies between EU countries and regions.

To meet these major challenges, the following policy related actions are recommended:

Recommendation 3.1

With regards to research and innovation policy, it is crucial to actively involve policymakers and other stakeholders in research and development actions, so that questions and issues related to policy and regulations are addressed from the very beginning. Emphasis on co-creation should be included in research and innovation work programmes.

Recommendation 3.2

The experience of projects demonstrates that policies based on data collected employing digital tools and systems (e.g. sensor systems) are always fairer and better explained and can achieve greater levels of acceptance. In addition, digital and IoT technologies used in the water sector allow the monitoring of water efficiently and accurately. This can be beneficial for the development of new regulations or the improvement of existing regulations given that such legislation can be based on the latest technological knowledge available. Therefore, data-driven approaches and the exploitation of the value of data for the water sector should be used to improve and design new policies, either by providing supporting evidence or as an implementation monitoring instrument. Furthermore, legal requirements to exploit the value of data for the water sector will enable the design of smart water management tailored solutions (optimisation, prediction, diagnosis, real-time monitoring).

Recommendation 3.3

Project practice proves that the heterogeneity of the national legislation among the member states regarding Managed Aquifer Recharge (MAR) often hinders promising applications of MAR technologies both in Europe and internationally. Therefore, consistent guidelines to use digital solutions for MAR could potentially improve the understanding of hydrogeological processes and could facilitate a more homogeneous implementation of MAR solutions in the EU member states and internationally.

Recommendation 3.4

To extend the transparency and efficiency of the decision-making processes in water management, the exploitation of the value of new digital solutions and combinations of those should be promoted.

Digital decision-support systems in the operation and management of water networks in urban and peri-urban areas have to be encouraged at local and regional level (or put as a legal requirement at the EC level).

Recommendation 3.5

To establish requirements within the UWWTD regarding the management and control of CSOs using digital solutions. For example, employing new modelling tools and methodological approaches for the pre-selection of highly vulnerable parts of the wastewater system can ensure the best use of cost-effective, real-time monitoring equipment.

4. THE CONTRIBUTION OF THE DIGITALISATION OF THE WATER SECTOR TO THE MITIGATION OF FLOODS, STORMWATER OVERFLOW (SWO) AND COMBINED SEWAGE OVERFLOW (CSO)

There are numerous digital applications available for specific parts of the water cycle in urban, rural or industrial areas. For example, digital applications addressing water management challenges across the entire water cycle can enhance the capacity of environmental monitoring to gather timely information. This can ultimately improve the control and understanding of the nature and dynamics of flood events, including better management of combined sewage overflows or control combined sewage overflows. Constant and regular observations enable detection of the occurrences and the prediction of flood duration. However, some existing modular digital solutions may have limited spatial coverage and temporal frequency that provides scattered or infrequent information for large-scale water networks, for example in urban areas. Therefore, the DWC project has developed large-scale low-cost online monitoring solutions to **increase the real-time accuracy in managing water cycles**. For example, **low-cost sensors**³⁶, developed for broader implementation in CSO structures, employ new, affordable digital surveillance technologies which are capable of reducing the CAPEX and OPEX of system observations by up to 2000 € CAPEX / CSO + operational costs. Moreover, they can offer more detailed data such as flow rate, water level, turbidity (the sediment content in water), photo or video footage for water network assets management which is used for structure integrity inspection, leakage and/or blockage detection, and illicit connection identification. This was tested by the SCOREwater project.³⁷

Information from sensor observations of flow attributes in the water networks and catchments can contribute to the calibration and validation of digital models for setting up smart CSO management networks, as does training for artificial intelligence (AI) based models (WISDOM³⁸). These approaches also **improve the accuracy of flood and water quality forecasting** (DWC³⁹) to support **real-time control of water networks** (SCOREwater⁴⁰, RECONNECT⁴¹ and PrimeWater⁴²). The use case of Damhusåen wastewater treatment plant in the DWC⁴³ project has frequent bypass events (on average more than 75 times per year), with untreated sewage spilling into the surface waters. Linking sensor observations with real-time control algorithms can result in the issuing of early warnings regarding flood events to support decision-making in order to mitigate hazard risks to human safety and health, damage to properties and infrastructure and the impact on socio-economic activities and environmental systems. During the period 1980-2017, the cost of floods and mass movements was on average 4,2 billion EUR per year in the EU-28 countries.⁴⁴ Modeling results can also support the **design of networks to optimise capacity** (CENTAUR⁴⁵) or the installation of control devices to prevent flooding (CENTAUR^{46,47}).

³⁶<https://www.digital-water.city/solution/low-cost-temperature-sensors-for-real-time-combined-sewer-overflow-cso-and-flood-monitoring>

³⁷<https://www.scorewater.eu/>

³⁸<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/8013727>

³⁹<https://www.digital-water.city/solution/sewer-flow-forecast-toolbox>

⁴⁰<https://scorewater.eu/news/16>

⁴¹<http://www.reconnect.eu/network-of-cases/elbe-estuary/>

⁴²www.primewater.eu

⁴³<https://www.digital-water.city/solution/interoperable-decision-support-system-dss-and-real-time-control-algorithms-for-stormwater-management/>

⁴⁴<https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/indicators/direct-losses-from-weather-disasters-3/assessment-2>

⁴⁵<https://zenodo.org/record/1051200#.X1ArIshKjtV>

⁴⁶<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2017.11.020>

⁴⁷<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/1573062X.2020.1860238>

Sensor data in digital applications can be provided by multiple sources with different formats. Apart from conventional solutions such as SCADA systems, rain gauges and radar, flow meters, and water quality sensors, various data collecting, processing and analytics methodologies can also provide or interpret information from other sources. For example, aqua3S⁴⁸ is employing unmanned aerial vehicles (UAV) and satellites, which can monitor and detect the occurrences of floods and droughts at a large scale. Aqua3S also has developed real-time social media data analytics tools to collect crowd sourcing information and evaluate hazard and flood-related keywords, as well as georeferenced citizen discussions to identify those incidents. Image recognition and machine learning may extract flood depth, velocity and extent from Closed Circuit Television (CCTV) footage or photos. This offers an excellent opportunity for citizen science approaches whereby observations from citizens are gathered (Ground Truth 2.0^{49,50}), and which, as a side effect, also raise public awareness regarding floods, pollution, environmental quality and degradation. In addition, the information from sensors can be used to quantify the potential impact of flooding and the cascading effects on critical infrastructures and services (EU-CIRCLE⁵¹ and RESCCUE⁵²) and promote risk communication with stakeholders such as municipalities, water authorities (NAIADES⁵³), citizens and farmers (Ground Truth 2.0⁵⁴) to enhance their knowledge about environmental risks. This permits improved dialogue and collaboration between different parties which in turn, can result in a policy-making consensus (POWER⁵⁵) and effective strategic planning (EU-CIRCLE⁵⁶ and RESCCUE⁵⁷), to promote sustainable water-resource management (RECONNECT⁵⁸ and SUBSOL⁵⁹) and the improved protection of ecosystems (GT2.0⁶⁰ and RECONNECT⁶¹). The aforementioned actions would contribute to the implementation of the Floods Directive and Water Framework Directive, including the climate change adaptation necessary measures.

Digital applications may serve multiple functions beyond the monitoring of floods and droughts. DWC⁶² has developed algorithms for sensor data profiling to identify illicit connections that may jeopardise the integrity of network functions. WISDOM⁶³ has constructed an automated model for CSO prediction that displayed an accuracy rate of 90% to support network operators' decision-making when seeking to alleviate the impact of CSO spillages. SCOREwater⁶⁴ has created wastewater overflow surveillance tools to highlight potential threats to the system and support predictive maintenance to prevent failures from occurring. Digital solutions also provide opportunities for innovation. For example, SUBSOL⁶⁵ has integrated sensor data and modelling assessment to strengthen

⁴⁸ <https://aqua3s.eu/the-project>

⁴⁹ <http://altena.gripopwater.nl>

⁵⁰ <http://mara.info.ke/>

⁵¹ <https://www.eu-circle.eu/>

⁵² <http://www.resccue.eu/>

⁵³ <https://naiades-project.eu/alicante-spain>

⁵⁴ <http://altena.gripopwater.nl>

⁵⁵ <https://doi.org/10.1080/1523908X.2019.1627864>

⁵⁶ <https://www.eu-circle.eu/>

⁵⁷ <http://www.resccue.eu/>

⁵⁸ <http://www.reconnect.eu/>

⁵⁹ <http://www.subsol.org/about-subsol/overview>

⁶⁰ <https://gt20.eu/cases/biodiversity-conservation>

⁶¹ <http://www.reconnect.eu/2020/06/30/environmental-monitoring-starts-in-aarhus/>

⁶² <https://www.digital-water.city/solution/low-cost-temperature-sensors-for-real-time-combined-sewer-overflow-cso-and-flood-monitoring>

⁶³ <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/8013727>

⁶⁴ <https://www.scorewater.eu/cases/goteborg-en>

⁶⁵ <http://www.subsol.org/home/article/urban-waterbuffer-supplies-water-to-sparta-stadium>

the operation of existing flood defence facilities thus maximising the capacity of systems to cope with floods and droughts.

To meet these major challenges the following policy-related actions are recommended:

Recommendation 4.1: Implement new digital technologies for the monitoring of water utilities' infrastructures and relevant environmental / weather conditions

The strengthening and appropriate alignment of existing water directives to encourage **the adoption of new digital technologies is required for the monitoring of the operational status of water utility infrastructures, including capacity, performance and asset conditions.** Moreover, the **employment of digital technologies should be encouraged for the monitoring of related environmental and weather conditions** (e.g. rainfall, surface runoff that adds a burden to an urban drainage network, or river/tidal level) thus improving management performance in relation to drainage networks. The information should be obtained in an adequate spatial and temporal parameter to enable real-time operation and effective predictive management.

Recommendation 4.2: Integrate the measurements (of 4.1) with modelling and data analytics to predict the performance of wastewater networks (urban/peri-urban) using standardised platform and information exchange protocols

Future policy should demand the **integration of the above-mentioned digital measurements with modelling and data analytics (e.g. machine learning and artificial intelligence) to predict the performance of wastewater networks in urban and peri-urban areas** and to determine the most appropriate operational strategies in order to reduce the occurrences of CSO and SWO. Such integration would require a **standardised platform and adequate information exchange protocols** to overcome barriers to data sharing and to promote practical knowledge exchange between data providers. This would accelerate subsequent applications in wastewater infrastructure operation and management. Standardisation would maximise the capacity of digital solutions that provide not only measurements but also enable **predictive management for both real-time control and long-term investment strategic planning** to mitigate floods and the associated impact to communities.

Recommendation 4.3: Require that utilities apply the above (4.1 & 4.2) for predictive maintenance and operation management

Policy should **require utilities to employ predictive maintenance and operation management** employing digital water surveillance and hydroinformatic analysis to support timely decision making, to enhance the reliability of services and infrastructures

and maximise the performance of stormwater and wastewater networks. Predictive management will benefit both water utility operators and the public by means of improved quality of the services and the reduction of health and safety risks to individuals, damage to properties, and disruption to businesses.

Recommendation 4.4: Ensure that all urban/peri-urban digital networks for water supply and wastewater are linked and are interoperable as one holistic operational system

Policy should ensure **that all urban/peri-urban digital networks for water supply and wastewater are linked and are interoperable as one holistic operational system**. This would ensure the integrity and resilience of the infrastructure and strengthen the holistic management of water networks. The interconnectivity and interaction between individual assets within a water network are vital for the successful implementation of digital solutions.

5. THE DIGITALISATION OF THE WATER SECTOR CAN CONTRIBUTE TO REDUCING ENVIRONMENTAL DAMAGE

Digital water is expected to reduce the environmental impact of water operations via a) **reductions in energy demand** (and the associated GHG emissions) of water supply and sanitation services; b) improved control of emissions from wastewater treatment plants; c) enhanced capabilities for real-time, in-situ water quality monitoring; and d) increased water-use efficiency across all sectors. While the surveyed projects provide solid evidence that digital solutions are enablers of these benefits, subsequent improvements in the status of water bodies and water-dependent ecosystems have not been thoroughly investigated. Conversely, there are recurring indications that technological developments are ahead of legislation and could therefore represent missed opportunities regarding the achievement of environmental policy targets and the uptake of more efficient water management solutions.

The analysis of environmental damage avoided by the implementation of digital solutions or **ICT-based management approaches requires the consideration of at least three impact levels**. The first level involves the **measurement of changes in resources** (e.g. water, energy, materials) abstracted and used in water cycle operations. The second entails the **quantification of the operations' discharges** into the environment (e.g. pollutants, effluent, GHG emissions). The third concerns the characterisation and **estimation of impacts** that the aforementioned changes in abstraction and discharge have on ecosystems. The direct nature of the first and the second impacts as well as the availability of established methods for their monitoring and estimation have allowed the research community to gather more concrete evidence. Conversely, wider and often indirect impacts on ecosystems, their functioning and the services they provide are generally more elusive and there is still a lack of widely-accepted methods for their quantification.

Integrated digital systems are at the core of the circular approaches proposed by projects such as Project Ô, SMART-Plant and NextGen. These projects have aimed at reducing abstraction and point-source pollution pressures by setting up small loops within water networks to open the accessibility of the reuse/ recycling of otherwise wasted resources such as waste and process water, fuels/energy and other materials. Project Ô has demonstrated rainwater and wastewater reuse by employing technologies that can inactivate bacteria and degrade hormones, pharmaceuticals and perfluoroalkyl substances (PFAs). This has been coupled with the principle objective of enabling the exploitation of alternative water sources for municipal supply, increasing efficiency and reducing pressures on water-scarce locations. Furthermore, SMART-Plant demonstrators have been successful in achieving up to 70% reductions in energy demand and the associated GHG emissions from municipal wastewater treatment processes⁶⁶. The demonstrated technologies can extract a significant amount of energy and materials from wastewater streams that can be used to substitute primary resources. Seen through the lens of the impact typology described above, these examples effectively represent reductions in resource abstractions from the environment together with a decrease in pollutant emissions. Such measures contribute to the improved implementation of the WFD,

⁶⁶ <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/1573062X.2020.1860238>

including the Drought Strategy and moreover, they enhance a shift towards a circular economy within water and water-related sectors.

Similarly, digital systems have been fundamental in the design and operation of **Decision Support Systems (DSS) that allow an enhanced effluent control** through the reuse of wastewater at precisely defined, fit-for-purpose quality levels in heavy-industry operations. This is the case of the INTEGROIL project⁶⁷, whose approach was demonstrated in downstream oil and gas operations and is now being adapted for application in the metallurgy sector. Here, the quality of process water is continuously monitored at different points of the operation. The system compares the data with the requirements of the intended water reuse application and activates the adequate treatment process accordingly. By closing this loop, such approaches can indirectly reduce the amount of pollution entering the environment.

As is the case with those mentioned above, most surveyed projects are adopting approaches that employ cost-efficient or low-cost sensors to enable the monitoring and control of water quality. By deploying such sensors in the water body (the case of DWC and INTCATCH) or in the wastewater treatment plant (Project Ô and HYDROUSA), **parameters such as E. Coli and Enterococci concentrations, turbidity and bacterial stress can be measured in real-time**. Furthermore, projects such as SCOREwater are combining these measurements with meteorological data to generate a timely overview of the status of stormwater and wastewater systems as well as that of receiving water bodies to allow for predictive control of wastewater treatment processes.

In broad terms, the role played by digital technology in the referenced projects has been to enable or improve the measurement of changes in water quality parameters and trigger reactive or predictive responses aimed at optimising operations and increasing climate resilience and resource efficiency. However, what this enhanced process control effectively represents in terms of ecosystem health and function, is still largely unexplored. The INTCATCH project, for instance, reported that a significant amount of monitoring was conducted to demonstrate the capacity of new sensors to detect certain pollutants - pesticides (tributyltin and pentachlorophenol), heavy metals, E. coli and other environmental bacteria - and of a new compact treatment plant for CSOs to reduce nutrient contamination and E. coli diffusion in coastal and sensitive areas. However, no evidence was collected regarding actual impacts of the project's novel integrated tools on ecosystems and the data gathered during the demonstrations has not yet been exploited to illustrate these issues.

One recurrent impression is that the focus of research has, to date, been largely placed on advancing the technical effectiveness, implementability and feasibility of the projects' digitally-aided management approaches and technologies, while **their wider impacts on the environment and water ecosystems often fell beyond the scope of the work plan**. While most projects devised elaborate strategies and activities to assess the impact of the technological applications on waste and process water treatment operations and the relevant parameters therein (e.g. via LCA & LCC approaches), an in-depth research is missing on, for example, freshwater ecology aimed at understanding how these parametric changes are reflected in natural systems at the catchment or sub-catchment level. The magnitude of such research questions coupled with the resources employed and the coordination effort necessary to address them would appear to explain this outcome.

⁶⁷ <https://integroil.eu/>

However, this diagnosis highlights the need for a stronger push towards transdisciplinary and more balanced R&I project agendas.

Finally, project coordinators often reported on the state of technical capabilities of the demonstrated solutions being beyond what current legislation requires. For instance, the approaches demonstrated by INTEGROIL and SMART-Plant enable the achievement of water-reuse levels and material recovery that are not yet requested by existing legislation. This results in a lack of uptake since industry and utility operators will, in most cases, comply only with that legally demanded but not beyond that.

To meet these major challenges the following policy related actions are recommended:

Recommendation 5.1

At an EU level, to **support the implementation of circular economy solutions** in water-utilities and water-intense industries, for example using the harmonisation of end-of-waste criteria for resources recovered from WWTP. An additional action would be to encourage zero-discharge resulting from industrial water use. In order to achieve the above, the exploitation of digitally-aided management approaches and technologies is essential.

Recommendation 5.2a

Update the legal requirements of the EU UWWTD regarding the control of pesticides, heavy metals and E.Coli so that they incorporate the new possibilities offered by digital solutions.

Recommendation 5.2b

Update the provisions of the WFD and other relevant water policies on environmental monitoring and resource efficiency so that they incorporate the new possibilities offered by digital solutions.

As demonstrated by the projects referred to, digital technologies are expanding the technical capacities of operators regarding water management, pollutant detection, energy efficiency and recovery, water reuse, and circular economy in urban wastewater treatment systems. Where the implementation of specific provisions has been slow or contended (e.g. environmental flows, polluter-pays-principle), this should be used to leverage progress. Where current targets are being met, an increase in their ambition that is proportionate to the new technical capacities should be considered.

Recommendation 5.3

In terms of **research and knowledge uptake, generate the conditions so that consortia of completed and ongoing projects open any data they have collected regarding changes in the ecological, chemical and quantitative parameters of water bodies.** This would help improve the future understanding of the relationship between ecosystem status, health and functioning.

Recommendation 5.4

In **addressing knowledge gaps**, it is recommended to **ensure and accelerate an enhanced understanding of the impacts of digital water on natural systems** that enables the uptake and tangible progress towards the achievement of the objectives of current EU environmental policy and the UN Sustainable Development Goals. Therefore, future research programmes would include actions that integrate applied and fundamental research more consistently (i.e. incorporating the development of feasible and exploitable technologies with the scrutiny of their impacts on natural systems). This would supplement and strengthen the progress achieved so far in making digital water solutions operational.

6. NOVEL COST-EFFECTIVE AND TIME-EFFICIENT SENSING TECHNOLOGIES FOR WATER QUALITY AND QUANTITY MONITORING

Large-scale, cost-effective and time-efficient sensing technologies for water quality and quantity monitoring are applied differently in distinct parts of the water sector. The online monitoring of BOD₅, COD, TSS, TOC, coliform, N, P and other substances (e.g. pollutants of emerging concern) is fairly widely used in wastewater treatment plants. There are, however, large differences as to how widely-used online monitoring is in different countries and wastewater treatment plants of varying dimensions. According to a recent study by IVL⁶⁸, the instruments are increasing in presence at wastewater treatment plants and they constitute an important basis for both monitoring and process control. For wastewater treatment plants, commercial sensors are available and there exists the potential to further test systems based on these sensors in new applications, as in the project HYDROUSA (E. Coli monitoring system for reclaimed water, dissolved methane in anaerobic effluents).

Nevertheless, other parts of the water sector, such as drinking water, the monitoring of surface and groundwater, small-scale treatment plants for dwellings and wastewater systems are still proving slow on the uptake and still rely to a great extent on monitoring by laboratory tests and manual samplings of BOD₅, COD, TSS, TOC, coliform, N, P and other substances or even no monitoring at all. However, the market for smart meters continues to be the largest and fastest-growing segment of smart water networks followed closely by leakage management solutions⁶⁹. As such, smart meter rollout is expected to dominate the market in the coming years, thanks to the relatively low cost of equipment and the ease of implementation.

Global inland and coastal water **monitoring through satellites**, as for example addressed by the MONOCLE and PrimeWater projects, is now sufficiently mature to deliver key information on biogeochemical cycling which includes the capability to monitor ecosystem response to changing nutrient loads with respect to a 10-15 year baseline. **Other remote sensing technologies** such as drones for online monitoring water stress and irrigation needs are under rapid development, as that, for example, developed by the project WADI⁷⁰. There is a potential to combine data from remote sensing technologies with on-site sensors to achieve more accurate and cost-efficient monitoring. This is to-date an unmaturing field that requires cross-sectorial cooperation.

There are many ongoing research projects investigating **cost-effective and time-efficient sensing technologies for water quality and quantity monitoring**. Examples include the projects SCOREwater (real time contactless turbidity and water level monitoring), DWC (real-time bacterial monitoring) and PrimeWater (advanced Earth-Observation data products integrated with additional data sources and diagnostic modelling tools). Early estimates in the SCOREwater project regarding the case study of Gothenburg suggests that the investment costs of a monitoring system based on sensors for predictive maintenance of wastewater systems in the city could be in the magnitude of **one tenth of the annual maintenance costs**. Today, the need for maintenance in wastewater systems is usually identified by manual inspection. This is very costly. If the sensors could have a multiple year maintenance-free lifetime, to ensure that the operational costs do not become excessive, the relatively low CAPEX of the system compared to the relatively high OPEX of maintenance suggests that just a few percent lower OPEX due to more efficient maintenance can make the system profitable. Furthermore, failure to identify clogging and

⁶⁸ Andersson, S. L., L. Åmand, O. Samuelsson and S. Nilsson, 2020. Instrumentera rätt på avloppsreningsverk. IVL Swedish Environmental Institute, Stockholm.

⁶⁹ GWI, 2017. Global Water Market 2017. Media Analytics Ltd, Oxford.

⁷⁰ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/689239>; <https://www.waditech.eu/>

sedimentation on time can lead to odour, overflow and make the impact of flooding events more severe, leading to the damage of properties and business.

The major challenge is not that the technology *with the potential* to be cost-effective and time-efficient does not exist (with the exception of microbiological pollutants, where there are technical challenges to accurately detect microbes in cost-efficient ways). The real challenge is to scale up such methodologies and to ensure that they prove truly cost-effective and time efficient.

- The online monitoring of pollutants is usually not a legal requirement for stormwater and combined sewage systems. There exists, therefore, little motivation for utilities and other actors to invest in sensing technologies for water quality monitoring. This challenge has been identified in the project SCOREwater when addressing the market of environmental monitoring of construction sites. Market analysis shows that the United States, where stricter regulations for monitoring pollutants of stormwater are in place, has a more thriving market and several growth companies commercialising sensing technologies. There are market-ready or near market-ready sensing technologies for turbidity, pH and conductivity.
- To make sensing technologies cost-effective, the sensors have to be produced on a large scale. The water sector is economically relatively small and, therefore, it is difficult to create a market based exclusively on this sector. Furthermore, the water market is fragmented⁷¹. This is made up of numerous utilities of varying sizes, each with unique problems in need of tailor-made solutions. The digital solutions market is itself fragmented⁷². A multitude of companies are specialising in niche applications: equipment manufacturers modifying physical equipment (e.g. pumps) for integration with the smart network; technology companies creating sensors; communications companies transmitting collected data; and data management and analytics firms providing analysis. Such divisions, coupled with a risk-averse culture, make adopting digital solutions an onerous task for many utilities and industry-wide standardisation difficult to achieve.
- Water utilities, especially drinking water utilities⁷³, many times **lack advanced data management skills**⁷⁴: large scale sensing technologies are built on 'big data', but the collection of relevant parameters is only part of the equation. Management and analysis of this data leading to meaningful insight are essential to make the sensing useful.
- The experience of the INNOQUA project⁷⁵ shows that wastewater systems (sewage, stormwater and combined sewage and stormwater) are harsh environments. Therefore it is a challenge to make the use of sensors time efficient. Even if a cost-efficient sensor could be produced, it has to be robust enough to require little maintenance, otherwise, a system of many sensors soon becomes costly in maintenance. Analysis in the SCOREwater project shows that a sensor that has no contact with the water is preferred as biological growth on sensors in water requires regular cleaning increasing costs.

⁷¹ GWI, 2017. Global Water Market 2017. Media Analytics Ltd, Oxford.

⁷² GWI, 2017. Global Water Market 2017. Media Analytics Ltd, Oxford.

⁷³ RISE, 2017. UDI – SENSATION III - Slutrapportering Steg 3 Följdinvestering. RISE, Göteborg.

⁷⁴ GWI, 2017. Global Water Market 2017. Media Analytics Ltd, Oxford.

⁷⁵ <https://innoqua-project.eu/>

To meet these major challenges, the following policy related actions are recommended:

Recommendation 6.1

Set legal requirements on **online monitoring of pollutants from stormwater and combined sewage and stormwater systems**. Start with some **key parameters such as turbidity, pH and conductivity** (technically viable and today on the market). Without such requirements, there will be little motivation for utilities and other actors to invest in sensor technologies for water quality monitoring. One interesting area to start with could be **the environmental monitoring of stormwater from larger constructions sites such as infrastructure projects**, since monitoring requirements regarding these projects already exist. Online monitoring with low-cost sensing technologies could also lead to the possibility of being obliged to monitor smaller construction sites, which discharge their rain runoff or wastewaters from construction sites into the urban wastewater networks. Currently, these may have only to produce qualitative environmental reports without measurements since laboratory testing is too costly. This would improve urban wastewater network management and the overall water quality of receiving water bodies, in particular, those located in urban areas.

Recommendation 6.2

Stimulate the **creation of a volume market for sensing technologies**. Policy action needs to focus on this because the upscaling of a fragmented market is a major barrier for many of the digital technologies in the water market. Initially, the focus should be placed on areas where the greatest demand could be expected and where the motivation is strongest, for example **concerning the optimising of OPEX/CAPEX. Predictive maintenance of wastewater systems** (sewage, stormwater and combined sewage and stormwater) is just such an aspect.

As an example, one policy instrument that has successfully addressed upscaling in fragmented markets in another sector is **Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP)**. PCP challenges industry from the demand side to develop innovative solutions for public sector needs and it provides a first customer reference that enables companies to create competitive advantages on the market. PCP enables public procurers to compare alternative potential solution approaches and filter the best possible solutions that the market can deliver to address the public need.

Recommendation 6.3

To further support a volume market, establish guidelines to employ sensing systems for predictive maintenance and flood control of wastewater systems (sewage, stormwater and combined sewage and stormwater) and start to work with standardisation when the market has become more mature.

Recommendation 6.4

Create **competence development programmes on advanced data management for the water sector**. This should be directed at both technical staff and management at utilities, urban administration level as well as at data experts in order to raise awareness regarding digital solutions and to attract them to the water sector. Both technical data skills and the management and analysis of data need to be focused on. It is most essential that competence development on advanced data management is directed towards drinking water utilities, where data management is far less developed than in wastewater treatment plants, who are more accustomed to handling data from many sensors and instruments in real-time.

Summary of recommendations

1.1: Citizen science to support monitoring should be fostered by local authorities and utilities.

1.2: Authorities should strive for collaborative tools to share monitoring data by using open data to minimise costs for partners and customers, offering transparency to all stakeholders involved.

1.3: National and supranational authorities should take the greatest advantage of existing satellite and geo-referencing infrastructures and encourage the use of innovative monitoring approaches in order to complement national and statutory monitoring and reporting.

1.4: Sustainable financing tools and investments (e.g., financing the digitalisation of utilities, including interoperability of different services) to support the *Twin Transition* and to reduce CAPEX/OPEX should be enhanced.

1.5: Authorities should include a requirement within public procurement procedures for the water sector whereby cost and benefit analysis that include estimates and the optimisation of OPEX/CAPEX.

2.1: Legislators/Authorities must ensure that end-user engagement in the co-creation and implementation of digital water initiatives is considered a priority to further guarantee a broad social awareness, acceptance and a subsequent political continuity.

2.2: European Commission services to further support the implementation of digital water technology in its role as an effective channel of communication. Information targeted at a broad audience must be actively encouraged.

2.3: The Joint Research Centre of the European Commission to establish educational courses designed for water professionals regarding social engagement to its full extent and adaptable to different geographical, technical and cultural realities at a river basin, regional and local level.

3.1: To actively involve policy and decision-makers and other stakeholders in the development of research and innovation policy actions and R&I work programmes.

3.2: Data-driven approaches and the exploitation of the value of data for the water sector should be used to improve and design new policies. Legal requirements to exploit the value of data for the water sector will enable the design of smart water management tailored solutions.

3.3: To establish/draft consistent guidelines on how to use digital solutions for managed aquifer recharge (MAR) in order to facilitate a more homogeneous implementation of MAR solutions in the EU member states and internationally.

3.4: To encourage the use of digital decision-support systems in the operation and management of water networks in urban and peri-urban areas at a local and regional level.

3.5: To establish requirements within the UWWTD regarding the management and control of CSOs by means of digital solutions (by employing new modelling tools and real-time monitoring digital tools and systems).

4.1: To require the employment of new digital technologies for the real-time monitoring of water utilities infrastructures (including capacity, performance and asset conditions) and for the monitoring of related environmental and weather conditions, in order to improve management performance of drainage networks.

4.2a: Integrate the measurements of digital monitoring with modelling and data analytics (e.g. machine learning and artificial intelligence) to predict the performance of wastewater networks (urban/peri-urban) using standardised platform and information exchange protocols and to determine the most appropriate operational strategies in order to reduce the occurrences of CSO and SWO.

4.2b: To establish a standardised platform and adequate information exchange protocols to overcome barriers to data sharing and to promote practical knowledge exchange between data providers in order to enable predictive management for both real-time control and long-term investment strategic planning.

4.3: To establish European requirements for utilities to employ the predictive maintenance and operation management and to apply 4.1 and 4.2 recommendations for that.

4.4: To ensure through policy requirements that all urban/peri-urban digital networks for water supply and wastewater are interconnected and linked into one interoperable and holistic operational system.

5.1: Support the implementation of circular economy solutions by means of the harmonisation of end-of-waste criteria for resources recovered from WWTP in water-utilities and water-intense industries, for which, the exploitation of digitally aided management approaches and technologies is essential.

5.2a: To update and/or introduce new legal requirements of the EU UWWTD regarding the control of pesticides, heavy metals, and E.coli so that they incorporate the new possibilities offered by digital solutions.

5.2b: To update the provisions of the WFD and other relevant water policies on environmental monitoring and resource efficiency so that they incorporate the new possibilities offered by digital solutions regarding water management, pollutant detection, energy efficiency and recovery, water reuse, and circular economy in urban wastewater treatment systems.

5.3: For research and knowledge uptake, to ensure that R&I project consortia open any data they have collected regarding changes in the ecological, chemical and quantitative parameters of water bodies to decision and policy-makers and other stakeholders.

5.4: In addressing knowledge gaps, to ensure and accelerate an enhanced understanding of the impacts of digital water on natural systems and in R&I work programmes include actions that integrate applied and fundamental research more consistently. This will enable the uptake of tangible progress to achieve the objective of the EU environmental policy and the UN Sustainable Development Goals.

6.1: Establish European legal requirements regarding the online (digital) monitoring of pollutants (e.g. by using low-cost sensing technologies) from stormwater and combined sewage and stormwater systems, starting with some key parameters such as turbidity, ph and conductivity that are technically viable and today on the market.

6.2: Stimulate the creation of a volume market for sensing technologies for the optimising of OPEX/CAPEX and predictive maintenance of wastewater systems.

6.3: Establish guidelines for the employment of sensor systems for predictive maintenance and flood control of wastewater and to start the work on standardisation.

6.4: To create competence development programmes (in particular in drinking water utilities, where data management is far less developed) on advanced data management for the water sector. To focus on the development of both technical data skills and the management and analysis of data.

Conclusion

The research undertaken by the Policy Action Group of ICT4WATER has provided in this document a series of recommendations based on careful investigation and a broad, open exchange of knowledge. There are no simple conclusions. Much study, as should always be the case, is still required as is the need to further the work of the partnerships whose results have been presented in this paper. This illustrates a common feature of subsidised projects which leads one to suggest that the funding authorities should demand that future proposals learn from and build upon the outcomes of previously finalised initiatives. Open research data is essential given that the understanding of the impact of digital water on natural systems must be improved.

Section 1 has demonstrated that the general costs of operation (OPEX) and the investment required in order to integrate new non-consumable aspects of an operation (CAPEX) can be reduced by careful planning, employing simulation and digital decision-support processes. Nevertheless, as is often the case in all sectors, the amount of initial investment required together with a perceived threat to utility security can prove to be an important obstacle that must be overcome. This can be addressed in several ways. The exploitation of future project results would most certainly benefit from the relevant entities being required to include a transparent Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) when submitting public tenders whilst further financial support from within the administrative mechanisms designed to achieve the Twin Transition are necessary. Of great importance is the need to ensure that utilities and all water-related stakeholders are aware of the possibilities offered by existing (and therefore previously paid) tools such as efficient satellite monitoring which would enhance their capability to comply with national statutory monitoring requirements.

Much of what is expounded in this document implies the importance of the role of digitalisation in achieving a more effective relationship with water end-users. It is important to distinguish between citizen science and citizen engagement. Both activities benefit from digital support. Whilst citizen science provides researchers with an effective alternative source of on-site data with the additional advantage of raising citizen awareness regarding local water issues, citizen engagement seeks to channel the citizen's enhanced awareness into a proactive involvement both in the co-creation and subsequent implementation of water-based policies (the methodology may be applied to almost any issue which is addressed by local or regional authorities). The effective use of Digital Social Platforms (DSPs) and Augmented Reality (AR) offer the water sector a wide range of exciting mechanisms to improve transparency and general public perception, capable of demonstrating in a clear and accessible manner both economic and practical benefits thus activating a common sense of purpose. Such practical communication and non-professional involvement result in a far broader social consensus providing a far more solid base for policy continuity. Effective communication is vital. A lesson that the water sector, which has rightly earned the unenviable reputation of being hermetic in the extreme, would do well to learn. Engagement must be embraced by all environmental actors including those traditionally expected to be purely technical and the European Commission must take action to ensure that entities such as utilities are correctly trained in such social-oriented activities.

Sections 3 and 4 of the paper coincide in declaring the importance of the water-monitoring capabilities of digital applications. Numerous technologies can improve both the design and implementation of water-based regulations by providing supporting evidence or as an implementation monitoring instrument, whilst also observing the true situation of infrastructures together with that of environmental and climatological conditions. The resulting data is more objective in its assessment and permits the optimisation of resources, a capacity to predict, diagnose and provide real-time information, which in turn enhances transparency and efficiency. Compliance with existing legislation such as the

WFD and the UWWTD is far more verifiable whilst the policy of pricing can be better adjusted to the reality on the ground by employing digital solutions. With regards to event prediction, it is essential that the measurements obtained are integrated with the appropriate modelling and data analytics on a standardised platform which would thus permit the establishment of clear information-exchange protocols. One of the important aspects which the contributors to this document highlight is the advantage of combining all urban and peri-urban digital networks into one holistic, operational and interoperable system, thus overcoming the obstacles presented by silo-style management within the same community. This would further contribute to the strengthening of the link between the Drinking Water Directive (DWD) and the Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (UWWTD) and to a coherent, holistic approach of integrated water management in urban and peri-urban areas. It would align the requirements of both directives whilst promoting an improved integration within the Water Framework Directive (WFD) and include further implementation of the principles of the circular economy.

Some challenges still need to be addressed. For example, the assessment of Combined Sewer Overflows (CSO) is difficult due to the physical number of wastewater pipes in any given urban area. The price of existing monitoring equipment can be dissuasive for modest operators and the application of systems such as smart meters varies greatly from one European country to another. Nevertheless, as Section 5 demonstrates, such applications do contribute to a tangible improvement in water operations which, in turn, can result in the reduction of environmental damage. A digital-water approach permits the enhanced control of emissions from wastewater treatment plants, improved real-time monitoring of water-based operations, enhanced reliability of water services, increased water-use efficiency and subsequently an important reduction in energy demand. Employing digital management technology, end-of-waste criteria can be harmonised thus mitigating resource abstraction and pollution, an important cornerstone of the circular economy. Such effects require administrative support in the form of revised directives capable of supporting digital solutions for the detection of pesticides, heavy metals, E. coli and other pollutants of emerging concern during recent months, or even viruses like COVID-19.

It is extremely important not to underestimate the negative effect that sectoral fragmentation coupled with an aversion to what is perceived as high capital expenditure has had on the incorporation into existing operational systems of much that has been discussed in this paper. The water sector, as has been indicated, is often guilty of not understanding the virtues and benefits of operational transparency nor the need for enhanced control. Although this is true of many sectors of human activity, water is an issue of such fundamental social, economic, and environmental importance that it demands a rapid and efficient series of solutions. As has been described in Section 6, the resistance on the part of operators to invest in, for example, applications to monitor pollutants from stormwater and combined sewage systems online will not be overcome unless required to do so by law. In the same way, given that the water market is not one of the commercially most attractive due to its reduced size, policy is required to ensure that a fragmented market is upscaled. As has been suggested, emphasis should be initially placed on aspects where there would be greater demand such as the optimising of OPEX and CAPEX and the employment of Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP) as a policy strategy is a recommendation that would establish a more sustainable market for digital technology suppliers. As is the case with citizen engagement and corporate transparency, European administrations must ensure that the water sector receives sufficient access to competence development programmes on advanced data management. Both the technical and managerial areas of a utility would benefit from such an approach. Just as importantly, so would society as a whole.

The description that was referred to in the Introduction regarding the ambitions of the present European Commission will be interpreted by many sectors through a thick lens of subjectivity. However, society cannot afford the luxury of a subjective water sector, just as it cannot ignore the fundamental importance of the most important of all the World's natural resources. Whilst countless manufacturers and service providers benefit from the advantages of the digital age, whether one industry or another fails to embrace the most recent advances does not endanger the future of society as a whole. The supply and the treatment of drinking water and wastewater, the control of stormwater, the monitoring of

both the quantity and the quality of this transparent element in the natural environment has always, does and will determine the health of the planet, the physical, social and economic well-being of society and the extent to which the ambitions of the Green Deal and the Twin Transition become the pillars of a new reality or are relegated in the future to the shelves of unfulfilled policy.

ICT4WATER CLUSTER PROJECTS

This document has been created with information provided by the following EU funded projects, all of whom, are members of the ICT4WATER Cluster:

	Project Acronym	Project Number	website
1.	AfriAlliance	689162	https://afrialliance.org/
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3.	AquaNES	689450	http://www.aquan-es-h2020.eu/
4.	B-WaterSmart	869171	https://www.kwrwater.nl/en/projecten/b-watersmart/
5.	CENTAUR	641931	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/641931
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32.	SUBSOL	642228	http://www.subsol.org/about-subsol/overview
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34.	WADI	689239	https://www.waditech.eu/
35.	WISDOM	619795	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/619795
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